

Multi-omics-based Biomarker Signatures of Dietary Carbohydrates Quality and Risk of Chronic Diseases

**Horizon Europe
Data Management Plan**

**NB! PLEASE GO THROUGH THIS DOCUMENT AND CHECK ITS
CONTENTS BEFORE SUBMITTING IT!**

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Data Management Plan created in Chalmers Data Stewardship Wizard «dsw.chalmers.se»
using Chalmers Horizon Europe DSW Knowledge Model v1.3.1 (chalmers:root-he:1.3.1).

History of changes

There are no named versions.

Contributors

The following contributors are related to the project of this DMP:

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Project(s)

We will be working on the following project(s) and for those are the data and work described in this DMP.

Funding

HORIZON EUROPE European Research Council (granted)

Action Number

101154245

Action Acronym

BISCUITS

Action Title

Multi-Omics-based Biomarker Signatures of dietary Carbohydrates qUAlITy and risk of chronic diseasesS

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2025-01-01

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2026-12-31

The prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2D), cardiovascular disease (CVD), and dementia is rapidly increasing worldwide and is therefore a major public health concern. Carbohydrate intake (40-80%) represents the main source of energy in most populations and the quality more than the quantity has a large effect on health. Recently, a “carbohydrate quality index” (CQI) emerged as a exposure that captures the combined and potentially synergistic effects of dietary glycemic index and intakes of total fiber, whole grains, and liquid or solid carbohydrates in a comprehensive manner. A high dietary carbohydrate quality assessed by the CQI has been associated with lower risk of T2D, CVD, and intermediate risk factors. However, the precise mechanisms of the associated beneficial effects offered by high CQI scores remain unresolved partially due to the lack of accurate biomarkers reflecting their exposure and the minimal information available on how CQI impacts the gut microbiota. The main objective of BISCUITS is to identify multi-omics signatures of dietary carbohydrate quality assessed by the CQI and evaluate their associations with the risk of chronic diseases in adult populations. We will integrate metabolomics and microbiota datasets using novel machine learning algorithms to identify combined panels of metabolites and microbial species reflecting the exposure to high CQI scores. We will also investigate the potential associations of these signatures with the risk of T2D, CVD, and dementia in two populations. Similar studies to this are not available in the literature and have the potential to discover novel biomarkers of CQI exposure and map biochemical mechanisms explaining the complex relationship between CQI and these diseases. This could open new avenues for the prevention and management of cardiometabolic and neurodegenerative diseases, resulting in easy-to-follow lifestyle recommendations and strategies that general population and patients can easily adopt.

1. Data Summary

Re-used datasets

We have found the following reference datasets that we have considered for re-use:

- **SIMPLER. Datasets on microbiota, metabolomics, blood biochemistry, dietary, lifestyle, and health questionnaires.**
(<https://www.simpler4health.se/w/sh/en>) ✓

Owner of this dataset: Swedish Infrastructure for Medical Population-based Life-course and Environmental Research – SIMPLER. Contact: simpler@surgsci.uu.se.

The provider keeps old versions around so the same reference data will be available to reproduce our results.

We will use the dataset as follows: For the purposes stated in the projec: To identify multi-omics signatures of dietary carbohydrate quality and evaluate their associations with the risk of chronic diseases.

- **ALL4DEM. Datasets on microbiota, metabolomics, blood biochemistry, dietary, lifestyle, and health questionnaires.**
(<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN52227045>) ✓

Owner of this dataset: Prof. Mònica Bulló Bonet. Universitat Rovira i Virgili. Department of Biochemistry and Biotechnology. Human Nutrition Unit. C/Sant Llorenç 21 Reus, Tarragona 43201 Spain. +34 977 77 99 48 Email monica.bullo@urv.cat.

The original dataset will be available both from the provider and from us together with our results for the reproducibility.

We will use the dataset as follows: For the purposes stated in the projec: To identify multi-omics signatures of dietary carbohydrate quality and evaluate their associations with the risk of chronic diseases.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **Text documents (.pdf and .docx)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

- **Markup language (.html and .md)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

- **Programming language and statistical data (.R, .Rmd and .Rda)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 2000 GB of data in this format.

- **Spreadsheets and databases (.txt, .csv and .xlsx)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

- **Raster images (.jpg, .tiff, .png)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 100 GB of data in this format.

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and T2D and CVD risk** (not published)
- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and dementia risk** (not published)

2.2. Making data accessible

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

The data cannot become completely open because of:

- legal reasons
- we want to publish a paper first

Concerning the legal reasons, a data sharing agreement will be required.

Data will be released only as soon as restrictions are falling away.

Metadata will be openly available including instructions how to get access to the data. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed (managed by the used repository / repositories).

We have a consortium agreement that arranges Intellectual Property.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **SIMPLER. Datasets on microbiota, metabolomics, blood biochemistry, dietary, lifestyle, and health questionnaires.** – available under specific restrictions, which we will follow in our project: Access to the datasets is part of a proposal previously submitted and approved by SIMPLER.
- **ALL4DEM. Datasets on microbiota, metabolomics, blood biochemistry, dietary, lifestyle, and health questionnaires.** – available under specific restrictions, which we will follow in our project: Access to the ALL4DEM cohort data will be done by using a data share agreement between the two partnering institutions: IISPV and Chalmers.

For our produced data, conditions are as follows:

- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and T2D and CVD risk** (not published)
- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and dementia risk** (not published)

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will be using the following standards (encodings, terminologies, vocabularies, ontologies):

- **UTF-8**

2.4. Increase data re-use

The metadata for our produced data will be kept as follows:

- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and T2D and CVD risk** (not published)
- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and dementia risk** (not published)

As explained in Section 2.2, our data cannot become completely open.

Due to privacy reasons, the data must stay in the same institute. We can use pseudonymization, anonymization, and data aggregation to make the data more openly available. For pseudonymization, we can make use of an existing 'trusted third party'.

There are IP reasons why our data can not be open. It is clear who owns data and documents.

Someone will be given the decision power to move documents or data to a new place after the project has finished.

3. Other research outputs

We use Data Stewardship Wizard for planning our data management and creating this DMP. The management and planning of other research outputs is done separately and is included as appendix to this DMP. Still, we benefit from data stewardship guidance (e.g. FAIR principles, openness, or security) and it is reflected in our plans with respect to other research outputs.

4. Allocation of resources

FAIR is a central part of our data management; it is considered at every decision in our data management plan. We use the FAIR data process ourselves to make our use of the data as efficient as possible. Making our data FAIR is therefore not a cost that can be separated from the rest of the project.

We will be archiving data (using so-called 'cold storage') for long term preservation after the project. The minimum lifetime of the archive is 10 years.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

5. Data security

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (<https://...>). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The risk of information loss in the project or organization is acceptably low. We will mitigate information leak risk for the project or organization. We will mitigate information vandalism risk for the project or organization.

We are not using any personal information.

We are running the project in a collaboration between different groups and institutes. A collaboration agreement that describes who can have access to what data in the project is set.

6. Ethics

Data we produce

For the data we produce, the ethical aspects are as follows:

- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and T2D and CVD risk** - *no information on personal nor sensitive data.*
- **Results on multi-omics signatures of carbohydrate quality exposure and dementia risk** - *no information on personal nor sensitive data.*

7. Other issues

We use the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) with its *Chalmers Horizon Europe DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: chalmers:root-he:1.3.1) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://dsw.chalmers.se/wizard> DSW instance where the project has direct URL: <https://dsw.chalmers.se/wizard/projects/8306ae0b-b686-4806-ba3f-62d6330381fc>.

We will not be using any extra national, funder, sectorial, nor departmental policies or procedures for data management.